

ECONOMICS OF FISHING GEARS FOR SUSTAINABLE FISH PRODUCTION AND DEVELOPMENT IN INLAND WATER BODIES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The economics of different types of fishing gears on lake Kainji had been analyzed. The result has shown that, all types of fishing gears in use on the lake have net returns that represent gains on the users investments, and on average, earned profits. Furthermore, the size of the net returns –gain, depends on the amount of user's investment and the profitability of each fishing method positively correlates with amount of input. The operational costs, catch and revenues did not only vary between different types of fishing gears in different localities but also in the same type of unit for each trip in the same locality. This paper highlights briefly the economics of different types of fishing gears operating on lake Kainji as an example of what may likely happen in other inland fisheries in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Inland fisheries, aquaculture , management strategies, potential yield, Nigeria,

INTRODUCTION

Inland fisheries management has become a difficult task in Nigeria due to mounting competition among fishers to catch as much as possible from the inland waters as a means of sustaining their livelihood. Resources management for maintaining sustainable production in inland fisheries requires indepth economic analysis of different production methods to ensure optimum exploitation, efficient marketing and development of alternative management strategies. Inland fisheries in Nigeria are not accorded priority in the development plans due to lack of political will and over-dependence on frozen fish importation. The potential yield from the capture fisheries and aquaculture is estimated to be around 3.2 million t/yr as against the current production of about 200, 000 t/yr (Miller, 2004).

It is estimated that contribution from inland and marine sector amounts to 200,000 and 300,000 tons respectively of the 500,000 tons of total Nigerian fish production (Abiodun et al, 2005). Even though the inland sector contributed nearly one third of the total fish production, its share to the total domestic supply was 60% in contrast to marine sector with 40% - high percent production is exported. Therefore, fish production from inland sector is of great significance as it contributes the major share in the protein rich food for domestic consumption. Inland fisheries management in Nigeria is very poor when compare with some of the developed inland waters in other countries. Lack of enhanced fish production, fishing gears and inland waters management measures seems to be greater impending factors in the development of a viable inland fishery in the country

A recent study of a typical inland fisheries at Lake Kainji in Nigeria shows, there are 4,100 fishers, 314 fishing localities with about 1,224 fish landing sites located all along 874 km length of shoreline of the Lake and various types of fishing gears are in operation on the lake (Abiodun and Niworu, 2004).

Surveys were conducted to collect data on cost of inputs, earnings and profits from six different types of fishing gears available on lake Kainji. These included gillnet, longline, driftnet, beach seine, cast net and trap fishing gears. The data collected on profits and costs were used for economic analysis of different boat- gear combinations. Old and new fishing gears were in operation and the capital investments on them vary considerably. Hence, the initial investments of different boat-gear combinations indicate the average resale value of the operating units during the study period.

This paper highlights briefly the economics of different types of fishing gears operating on Kainji Lake as a model for other inland water bodies.

Fig. 1. A map of Lake Kainji, Nigeria showing catch sampling stations

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

Lake Kainji (Fig. 1) is situated between latitudes 9° 50' – 10° 57' North and longitudes 4° 25' – 4° 45' East. The lake was impounded in August, 1968 and it is 134 km in length and 24.1 km in width. Its surface area has been variously quoted as approximately 1,270 km² (du Feu and Abiodun, 1998). The number of fishing settlement was 19 before the impoundment (Jenness, 1973) and rose to 314 in 2000 (Abiodun, 2001).

Currently, there are about 4,100 fisherfolk engaged in active fishing on the lake using different boat-gear combinations of varying levels of investment. Also there are about 7,127 fishing boats, 585 motorized and 6,542 non-motorized with about 6,977 gill nets, 1,638 cast nets, 909 drift nets, 5,003 longlines, 19,106 fish traps and 325 beach seine. Gill net, cast net, drift net and beach seine are all measured in bundles (A bundle is 91 meters of unmounted netting material) while one longline is 100 hooks. As against the estimated maximum sustainable yield of 18,750 t of fish, the lake currently yields 13,351 t of fish with an average annual catch of 3.2 t per fisherman. The fisheries of this lake are presently exploited at about 29% below its maximum sustainable yield (Abiodun, 2001).

Table 1: Estimated returns to gears in use in Naira.

1	2	3	4	5	6
Gill net	₦24,590.24	₦ 13,158	₦ 5,970	₦ 19,128	₦ 5,462.24
Longline	₦ 16,267.45	₦ 1,456	₦ 1,893	₦ 3, 249	₦ 13,018.45
Drift net	₦ 71,276.40	₦ 6,516	₦ 5,159	₦ 11,675	₦ 59,601.04
Beach seine	₦ 423,297.77	₦ 22,664	₦ 12,053	₦ 34,717	₦ 388,580.77
Cast net	₦ 62,246.79	₦ 2,160	₦ 2,186	₦ 4,346	₦ 57,900.79
Trap	₦ 3,104.67	₦ 894	₦ 1,613	₦ 2,507	₦ 597.67

Note: 2 = Annual gross earnings
 3 = Total fixed cost
 4 = Total Variable cost
 5 = Total cost of input
 6 = Annual net returns

Table 2: Relative comparison of cost of operation and net returns to gross earnings of individual gears.

1	2	3	4	5	6
Gill net	129%	29%	78%	350%	22%
Longline	501%	401%	20%	25%	80%
Drift net	611%	511%	16%	20%	84%
Beach seine	1219%	1119%	8%	9%	92%
Cast net	1432%	1332%	7%	8%	93%
Trap	124%	24%	81%	419%	19%

Note: 2 = Annual gross earnings as a percentage of cost of input
 3 = Annual net returns as a percentage of cost of input
 4 = Cost of input as a percentage of gross earnings
 5 = Cost of input as a percentage of net returns
 6 = net returns as a percentage of gross earnings

A stratified random sampling procedure was used to select 60 out of 314 fishing localities where semi-structured questionnaires were administered. The stratification is based on the similarity in the habitat characteristics (after Ita, 1982). This also reflects similarity of the type of fishing gears and canoes used in each stratum. A total of 650 out of 1020 fishermen were randomly selected from the 60 selected fishing localities and were interviewed by enumerators. The operational costs and earnings of sampled fishing gears were observed continuously for a period of one year, April 2006 to April 2007, covering both dry and rainy seasons. Data were collected on variables considered for estimating the fixed and operating costs, the gross and net returns to each of the fishing gears. The Nigerian-German Kainji Lake Fisheries Promotion Project (GTZ) also provided secondary data used in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ECONOMICS OF VARIOUS FISHING GEARS

Cost of Operation

All types of fishing gear in use on Lake Kainji have been included in the economic aspect of the fishing operation. In inland fishing, almost all types of fishing methods are sustained due to low level of investment requirement and also due to the family- enterprise nature of operation. In terms of cost of operation, the following variables are considered; age, purchase price, depreciation and present value of each gear and boat used to operate the gear as well as the labour per man-day. From the cost of input, Beach seine has the highest cost of operation (₦34,717), followed by the Gillnet (₦ 19,128), the Driftnet (₦ 11,675), Cast net (₦ 4,346), Longline (₦ 3,249) and Trap (₦ 2,507) respectively. The cost of operating one Beach seine is, for instance about twice that of Gillnet, thrice that of Driftnet and eight times that of Cast net (Table 1).

Net Returns and Gross Earnings

The net return on Gillnet represents a 29% gain on the users' investment. This indicates that the gross earnings of an individual Gillnet are more than the cost of operation. The gross earnings represented 129% of the cost of operation while a comparative analysis of the cost of operation to gross earnings yielded a value of 78%. That is, the gross earnings is 22% more than the cost of operation. The net return on Longline represents 401% gain on the users' investment. The cost input in this gear is very low. However, the gear is selective and thereby associated with high valued fish species that attract high price. This also indicates, the gross earnings of an individual Longline is more than the cost of operation. The gross earnings represented 501% of the cost of operation while a comparative analysis of the cost of operation to gross earnings yielded a value of 20% (i.e the gross earnings is 80% more than cost of operation). Also the return of Beach seine net is approximately eleven times its cost of input, that is, 1119% the cost of input. For Drift and cast net, they are 511% and 1232% respectively (Table 2).

From the comparative analysis of the cost of operation to gross earnings, Beach seine, Drift net, Cast net and Trap yielded a value of 8%, 16%, 7% and 81% respectively. That means, the Beach seine (92%), Drift net (84%), Cast net (93%) and Trap (19%) are more than the cost of their operations respectively (Table 2)

From this analysis, it can be inferred that all types of fishing gears on Kainji Lake, on average, earned profits. The manifold increase in the price of most inland fish in very recent years is mainly responsible for better rates of returns.

GN = Gill net, LL = Longline, DN = Drift net, BS = Beach seine, CN = Cast net and TR = Trap
 Fig. 2. The cost and earnings of individual fishing gear on Lake Kainji

The noticeable trend from this economic analysis showed that the Beach seine net, which required the highest investment, also yielded the highest return (Fig 2). For the Gillnet, Cast net and Drift net which require a lower investment and yielded a return of about 129%, 409% and 467% respectively may earn much better returns if more funds are put into them. These could fall within the reach of an average fisher involved in capture fisheries in Nigeria. It is also observed that, the survival and sustenance of different harvesting methods of capture fisheries depends largely on their profitability, which is interlinked with market demand and prices of different varieties of fish.

SUSTAINING INLAND FISHERIES PRODUCTION

Economics of different types of fishing gears in use on Kainji Lake indicate that they earn profits as their net returns surpassed their cost of operations. However, the beach seine net, which yielded the highest return is the most highly resource endangering gear on the lake due to its destructive effects on the fish juveniles. In order to sustain fish production on this lake, the use of beach seine to crop fish on the lake had been banned and should not be encouraged on any inland water body in Nigeria. Also gillnet, driftnet and cast net required low investment and yielded high net returns. It is noticeable that most of these gears are undersized and due to open access of inland fisheries they are largely used on the lake. An awareness campaign on the importance of the use of recommended mesh size is therefore a requirement for responsible fisheries in inland water bodies in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Cost and earnings investigation of fishing gears and craft in use on Kainji Lake showed that the Beach seine net, which required the highest investment, also yielded the highest return. This notwithstanding, the use of beach seine to crop fish on this lake had been banned and should not be encouraged on any inland water in Nigeria due to its destructive effect on the fish juveniles. Also it has been shown that the size of the net- returns- gain, depends on the amount of users investments and the profitability of each fishing method positively correlates with amount of input.

POLICY RECOMMENDATION

The traditional fishers involved in inland fishing are caught in a low income trap due to their low investments capacities, which in turn bring low net returns from capture fisheries. Therefore, integration of small-scale aquaculture with an improved investment in inland fisheries is a viable alternative to increase the present level of production from capture fisheries. Also, awareness campaigns should be conducted at all fishing localities on the importance of mesh size regulations and avoiding harvesting juvenile fish for sustainable fish production.

Finally, the fishers in each fishing locality require a comprehensive programme for their socio-economic improvement and development so as to achieve increased fish production and sustainability of inland fisheries.

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